

**COMPARATIVE STUDY ON EMPLOYEES' PERCEPTION TOWARDS
COMPENSATION AND BENEFIT POLICY:
THE CASE OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE COMMERCIAL BANKS IN
GURAGE ZONE**

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List of Abbreviation and Acronyms

ANOVA	-	Analysis of variance
CBE	-	Commercial Bank of Ethiopia
DFC	-	Direct financial compensation
IDFC	-	Indirect financial compensation
SNNPR	-	Southern Nations and National Peoples Reign
SPSS	-	Statistical Package for Social Science

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was Comparative Study on Employees Perception towards Compensation and Benefit Policy of Government and Private Commercial Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia". The population of the study was all employees working in Comercial bank of Ethiopia and Nib international banks of Gurage Zone, Ethiopia. Stratified random sampling was used based on the different size of the sample frame in which 168 staffs were participated on the study. The researcher used descriptive and explanatory research design and the required data were collected using questionnaire. The reliability was estimated using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient and the results were between 0.60-0.70 which show acceptable level values. The obtained data were analyzed using T-test analysis. The analysis revealed that the level of respondent's perception of fairness, effectiveness, decision and administration, and compensation and benefit policies significantly different in Comercial Bank of Ethiopia and Nib International Bank. In conclusion, perception levels of employees towards compensation and benefit significantly different in Comercial bank of Ethiopia and Nib international bank. Based on the findings, the study recommended the management of the bank to apply rule and regulation that focus on the real need of employee needs; and made compensation and benefit increment within logical time period; compensation and benefit rule and regulation should be periodically updated and communicated; participation of employees in compensation and benefit decision process; periodic evaluation of compensation and benefit effectiveness; and link organization strategic plan with compensation and benefit policy.

Keywords: Benefit, compensation, Direct Compensation, Gain-sharing, Indirect Compensation, Perception, Promotion, Salaries, Wage

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Study

A bank is believed to significantly contribute to the dynamic development of a country's economy. It as part of the financial system, involves the provision of maturity intermediation, risk reduction via diversification, reduction of information processing costs, and provision of payment functions (Fabozze et al., 2005). In a competitive environment, to be competitive enough in the market, banks need sustained high level of performance through their human resources. So, organization success rests on its employees that the necessity to worry on components is that it may impact on employees' motivation and performance (Liao et al., 2007).

It is crucial for organization to strategize their competitive and benefits plans in order to attract and retain appropriate talent of workers, maximize return on human capital and increase employees' job satisfaction. Hence, compensation and benefit policy is a powerful tool of an organizational goal achievement that makes employees become partners in their success (Pam, 2007).

According to Bozeman and Gaughan (2011), the perception of being paid what one is worth predicts job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is a positive feeling and favorable attitudes of people about their job resulting from evaluation of the job based on the job holder requirements and/or expectation. Job satisfaction has three dimensions. These are an emotional response to job situation, degree of feeling of meeting expectations and it represent several related attitudes or affective response (Luthans, 2011). According to Budhwar and Debrah, (2001), job satisfaction is a major indicator of employee feeling towards their job and can be used to predict employee behavior at work.

In most cases employees are willing and cooperative to do their job to the best of their abilities if they believe that pay is relatively equitable to performance. In other words compensation and benefits affects employee's decision to stay or leave an organization, to work effectively and accept additional responsibility (Bratton & Gold, 1995). So, the compensation and benefit policy should encourage workers to remain long period in organization, and increase motivation and commitment to the organization and thus increase the productivity of an organization (Brickley et al., 2002).

Compensation and benefit policy is what employees receive in exchange for their contribution to the organization. It involves design, development, implementation, communication and evaluation of the reward strategy and processes of the organization. It is the sum total of all forms of payments and rewards provided to employees for performing tasks to achieve organizational objectives (Sarika, 2016).

Compensation and benefit policy is designed to affect the perception of employees of a company. Best designed compensation and benefit policy affect the motivation of the employees to work. If the management of a company put an effort in identifying the need of employees and succeed on satisfying the needs by providing relevant compensation and benefit program then the motivational level of employee will increase towards the best achievement of job related activities (Ale et al., 2010). Similarly, poor compensation and benefit policy will lead to low performance and that will lead to low satisfaction level of employees' in turn will increase absenteeism and decrease the outcome (Feraro, 2017).

According to DeNisi and Griffin (2001) compensation and benefit is a reward system that a company provide to individuals in return for their willingness to perform various jobs and tasks within organizations. Similarly, according to Milkovich and Newman (1999), compensation refers to all forms of financial returns and tangible services and benefits that employees receive as part of an employment relationship. Likewise, The Journal of Global Business and Economics (2010) also defined compensation as “the combination of all cash incentives and the fringe benefits mix that an employee received from a company which constitutes an individual’s total compensation.”

Compensations and benefits are basically of two types, financial and non-financial and through using these two types; personnel’s conducts towards their works can be enriched in a positive way. Financial rewards means remuneration for enactment such as performance bonus, job promotion, commission, tips, gratuities and gifts etc. A non-financial reward means non-monetary or non-cash and it is a social acceptance such as recognition, certificate, and genuine appreciation (Luthans, 1998). However, according to Gary (2004) benefits are any indirect financial and non-financial payments that employees receive for continuing their employment with the company. According to him the most common benefits are medical, disability, life insurance, retirement benefits, fringe benefits and supplemental pay-sick leave and vacation leave.

According to (Nadimara, 2006), wages and salaries are the remuneration paid or payable to employees for work performed on behalf of an employer or services provided; bonus is an extra payment over and above salary and it acts as an incentive to perform better; a tip is a payment received for providing an excellent service; promotion is attached with increase in pay, and this motivates the employee to perform better. Social security provides income for retirees, the disabled and survivors of deceased workers (Gomez et.al., 1995); medical insurance provides medical care, income continuation and rehabilitation expenses for people who sustain job-related injuries or sickness (Heneman et.al., 1996).

According to Heneman et al. (1997) there are two major types of paid off which are vacations and specific days, such as holidays and days to perform civic or personal activities. The many risks encountered throughout life illness, accident, and early death among other things can be offset by buying insurance (Ivancevich & Glueck, 1989). Pensions provide income after retirement and until death based on the employee's years of work and direct pay. In addition to pensions, most employers offer some form of health insurance to retire (Tyson & York, 1996).

According to Munap et al. (2013) study all organizational compensation and benefit contributed to employees' satisfaction while salary is the predictor that significantly contributes to job satisfaction, among employees. Organizational compensation and benefits have a positive relationship with job satisfaction. Likewise, according to Rehman et al. (2013) there is a positive relationship between compensation and benefit, and job satisfaction. Moreover, according to Ermiyas (2017) study, direct financial compensation was one common cause of turnover and indirect financial compensation and non-financial compensation is less likely to cause turnover.

Taking this in to account managers and policy makers of banks in both private and public banks must understand employees' perception towards compensation and benefit policy and their degree of influence that the researcher is interested to study employees' perception towards compensation and benefit policy to fill the knowledge gap of leaders, managers and policy makers of these banks.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

According to Dogan (2009), the accomplishments of an organization is to build a workforce in which employees feel included, welcomed and work together with mutual respect in order to enhance individual and organizational productivity. Likewise, employees want their performance to be appreciated and providing appropriate compensation and benefits package which is effective medium not only to achieve organizational goals but also to ensure continuation of relationship with talented employees in the organization (Sabo, 2011).

According to Beruk (2013), as the banking industry expands, the competition among various banks become intensive; as a result retention of skilled manpower becomes a great challenge that affects their sustainability. Currently, there is competitive labor market for the banking industry that avail job opportunities with attractive compensation system are very important. And as cost of living is swiftly increasing with each passing day, employees are seeking better remuneration in other relevant banks, if they found inequity in their existing one. It is obvious that, new banks join the market and existing banks expand the network of their branches. So, new bank establishment and existing banks expansion may lead the competition gets tougher and recruiting and retaining qualified and experienced employee in tight job market become often pose up as a great challenge for the bank.

Compensation and benefit policy of an organization needs to be adequate in attracting, motivating and retaining competent employees. It should enable employees cope with the cost of living and improve their performance and productivity. Compensation system should be designed and implemented in a way that is equitable, transparent and consistent. Organizations need to inform their employees about compensation and benefits policy (Crawshaw, 2014).

According to Organ and Ryan (1995) job satisfaction enhances organizational citizenship behaviors. Moreover, it enhances employees' retention level and avoids the cost of hiring new ones (Murray, 1999). It has also been demonstrated that satisfied employees have better health and long live and satisfaction on the job carries over to the employee's life outside the job. From the management point of view satisfied work force translates in to higher productivity due to fewer interruption caused by absenteeism or good employees quitting (van derzee,2009).

Stakeholders have difficulties in attempting to create a clear and appealing strategy that can be used for the implementation of sound compensation and benefit policy for ensuring the preservation of job satisfaction (Petrescu & Simmons, 2008). According to Ejiofor and Anigho (1984) if there is a demonstration of dissatisfaction in workers' compensation and benefits, it makes workers mind change in their effort which result into low performance. Hence, the strategic use of compensation and benefits policy is one of the most important factors for employees' job satisfaction and then organizational performance.

According to Khan and Parveen (2014) research finding of job satisfaction among private and public workers which is conducted among Indian private and public bank workers job satisfaction through some key factors like salary; promotion and training. The research showed that job satisfaction of public sector bank employees was significantly higher than the private sector bank employees; satisfaction regarding salary, compensation and benefits was significantly higher among the private sector bank employees than the public sector bank employees; and satisfaction regarding promotion was significantly higher among the private sector bank employees than the public sector bank employees.

According to Mojumder (2012) study, all HRM dimensions exercised in the private banking sector of Bangladesh were not satisfied to the employees equally. Most of the employees were dissatisfied with compensation package followed by reward and motivation. Likewise, Hakan (2013) carried out a study in Karaman, Turkey and he found that public workers were not satisfied in wages, promotion and appreciation. Similarly, according to Ayalkbet (2013) study in analysis of the causes, consequences and management of employees' turnover in the commercial bank of Ethiopia, the study revealed that employees were dissatisfied with banks competitive pay system, salary and benefit policy. Also, Senayit and Assefa (2014) study showed that more than 65% of CBE employees were not satisfied on their job due to different reasons especially on salary payment and different advantages. Alike, Yenewub (2017) study on the title assessment of employees job satisfaction and she found that employees were not satisfied on salary and benefit packages.

Conversely, Dhanonjoy (2016) carried out a research on the title of job satisfaction of Commercial Bank Employees in Bangladesh. The study revealed that the majority of the respondents were found satisfied with their jobs. But Salary faceted was reflecting the lowest satisfaction levels. In addition, Islam and Saha (2001) in their study concluded that job satisfaction of bank officers was significantly dependent upon salary and fringe benefit.

Additionally, Islam et al. (2012) in their study investigated that job satisfaction among employees of all public and private commercial banks in Bangladesh. The study determined that morale and job satisfaction plays a vital role in overall performance of the employees in the workplace. It was also determined that pay, decision making authority, and promotional policy were the three top priorities for improving the work environment.

Furthermore, Tamrat (2016) carried out a study on assessment of employee job satisfaction in the case of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia and he found that majority of the employees in CBE were satisfied by their basic salary. Moreover, the study of Girmachew (2019) on the title of comparative study on job satisfaction level of private and public banks, the study showed that based on compensation and benefits private employee were more satisfied than public banks. Hence, because of contradictory results on employee job satisfaction on compensation and benefit policy further research should be conducted to verify the results of existing research.

Furthermore, according to Obiero (2012) study, salary and benefits policy of the organization showed very strong correlations to staff turnover and promotions, and positively influenced staff turnover. Likewise, according to Pitr (2020) study in Nepalese Commercial Banks, compensation is influencing factor for employees' turnover intention. Similarly, according to Mikiyas (2020) study in the commercial bank of Ethiopia, the study found that low salary and benefit was among the reasons of employee turnover in the bank. Hence, planned use of compensation and benefits policy is one of the most important factors to reduce employee turnover intention and employee turnover that further research should be conducted.

Daniel (2017) carried out study on the title of the effects of rewards and recognition on employee performance in public educational institutions, in Kenya, Kenyatta University, and he recommended further research on comparative studies should be conducted for private and public sectors. Likewise, Atakilti (2020) carried out study on the title of impact of compensation on employee

performance in private and public hospitals in Tigray, Ethiopia, and he recommended further research should be conducted to strengthen the findings of his research. In addition to this, Shakespeare (2011) and Chang (2015) stated that academic as well as empirical researches with regard to banking institution in Ethiopian context were limited and they recommended further. Hence, because of different researchers' recommended further research on compensation and benefit policy and banking institution that further research should necessary.

Furthermore, the researcher done unstructured interview on employee's job satisfaction in Gurage Zone commercial banks on compensation and benefits policy and some employees says they are satisfied and they will not want to leave their organization but the other employees says they are not satisfied especially on salary and they will want to leave their organization if there is any possibility. This unstructured assessment shows that there is a gap on job satisfaction of employees. For this reason that further research needs on the topic area to understand the employees perception.

Moreover, the researcher undertakes unstructured assessment of employees' turnover in commercial bank of Ethiopia and Nib international bank in wolkite cities branches. According to human resource department (Feb, 2022), the 5 years (2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, and 2021) voluntary employees' turnover were 1.5%, 2.3%, 2.8%, 3.1%, and 4.2% clerks or officer in commercial bank of Ethiopia and 0.8%, 1.1%, 1.6%, 1.9%, and 2.2% cleric or officer in Nib international bank, respectively. Accordingly, the deliberate use of compensation and benefits policy is one of the most important factors to reduce employee turnover that further research should be conducted.

Besides, as the knowledge of the researcher there is no sufficient academic literature in Ethiopia in the area of employees' perception towards compensation and benefit policy. Therefore, to fill such gaps, more academic research that focuses specifically on employees' perception towards compensation and benefit policy has very importance. So, this study aims to answer the question "Is there significant difference in perception level of employees towards compensation and benefit policy between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?"

1.3. Research Questions

1. Is there significance difference in perception level of employees towards effectiveness of compensation and benefit between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?
2. Is there significance difference in perception level of employees towards fairness of compensation and benefit between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?
3. Is there significance difference in perception level of employees towards compensation and benefit decision and administration between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?
4. Is there significance difference in perception level of employees towards overall compensation and benefit policy between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?

1.4. Objective of the Study

1.4.1. General Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to determine if there is significance difference between perception levels of employees towards compensation and benefit policy of government and private banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?

1.4.2. Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this particular study was:

1. To determine if there is significance difference in perceptions level of employees towards fairness of compensation and benefits between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?
2. To determine if there is significance difference in perceptions level of employees towards effectiveness of compensation and benefits between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?

3. To determine if there is significance difference in perceptions level of employees towards compensation and benefit decision and administration between Government and Private Banks employees in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?
4. To determine if there is significance difference in perceptions level of employees towards overall compensation and benefit policy between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?

1.7. Scope of the Study

It will be better to study all the commercial banks in Ethiopia but because of time and money constraints, the researcher was limited the scope of the study only to Gurage Zone government and private commercial Banks. Likewise, the researcher selected only Commercial Bank of Ethiopia from the government banks and only Nib International Bank from the private banks in Gurage Zone because these banks established or existed much earlier than other banks or they are the first banks of Gurage Zone. Similarly, the researcher motivated to comparative study on employees' perception towards compensation and benefit policy excluding management body of the selected banks since the researcher confirmed from the banks that turnover of the management body is not that much problems on the selected banks.

Likewise, the researcher motivated to comparative study on employees' perception towards compensation and benefit policy based only on fairness, effectiveness, decision and administration, and overall compensation and benefit policy since it showed practical similarity and difference between the selected banks. Moreover, cross sectional survey was used to collect all relevant data at a single point in time.

1.8. Organization of the Study

The study is organized in five chapters. Chapter one is introduction part of the document; it is comprised of background of the study, statement of the problem, research questions, and objective of the study, significance of the study, scope of the study, limitations of the study and definition of key terms. Chapter two deals about the literature review which mainly constitutes the theoretical and empirical reviews. Chapter three describes the research methodology that will be applied to conduct the study. It try to address the research design, target population, sample design, data source, data collection techniques and instruments, data analysis procedures, and potential ethical issues of the

study. Chapter four deals about data analysis and interpretation of the results and finally chapter five set up summery of findings, conclusion, suggestion and recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURES

2.1. Theoretical Literature Review

2.1.1. Concept of Compensation

Compensation is designed to encourage performance of individual's regardless of the different type incentives form used. Its play an active role in pushing forward individual's capacity and moving abilities, motivating them to develop their skills, and balance between organization requirements and the individuals' needs which enhance the organization performance efficiently and effectively (Marwan, 2012).

Compensation can have a direct impact on employee retention. While employers may use employee incentives and monetary rewards to retain employees, there are ways to complement compensation that have a much greater impact. Based on the type of compensation, along with the terms and conditions of an employee compensation package, an employer can boost employee retention (Dessler, 2011).

Employees are the backbone of an organization. The attainment of organizational objectives largely depends on the motivation of employees to work. Among other things employees are motivated to work when they are provided a fair financial and non-financial compensation for service rendered to the organization. Compensation refers to any factor which may be financial or non-financial that enables or motivates a particular course of action .Adequate incentives have been found one of the means through which organization can adopt to motivate employees and increase their workers" performance (Olubusayo, 2014).

Compensation is the remuneration received by an employee in return for his/her contribution to the organization. It is an organized practice that involves balancing the work-employee relation by providing monetary and non-monetary benefits to employees. Compensation is an integral part of human resource management which helps in motivating the employees and improving organizational effectiveness. Compensation is the human resource management function that deals with every type of reward individuals receive in exchange for performing organizational tasks. Money and benefits received may be in different forms-based compensation in money form and various benefits, which may be associated with employees service to the employer like provident fund, gratuity and insurance

scheme, besides any other payment which the employees receives or benefits he enjoys in lieu of such payment (Saiyadain, 2003).

Compensation is a reward for service rendered by people at work place (Dunn and Rachel, 1971). According to Stahl (1995), compensation is the monetary payments (wages, salaries emoluments, bonuses-current and deterred) used to reward employees.

Compensation is systematic way to providing monetary value to employees in exchange for their performance (SHRM, 2012). To determine compensation, organizations should develop a compensation and rewards program. This type of program outlines an equitable process for compensating employees. A well-structured program with a good balance of pay or salary structure and rewards will support an organization to remain competitive in today's labor market and ensure sustainability in future.

Compensation systems are designed keeping in minds the strategic goals and business objectives. It is usually designed on the basis of certain factors after analyzing the job or work and responsibilities. Compensation systems in organizations must be aligned to organizational objectives and strategies and also requires balancing the interests of the employer with the expectations of employees (Gebremedhin, 2013)

2.1.2. Types of Compensation

In order to create incentives for employees to achieve the organization's goal, different types of compensation system are used. By definition, compensation can be understood as total amount of the monetary and non-monetary reimbursement provided to an individual in return for labor. There are three general varieties of compensation including direct, indirect and non-financial.

2.1.2.1. Direct (Financial) Compensation

Financial compensation is regarded as variable payments made to employees or a group of employees on the basis of the amount of output or results achieved. Alternatively, it could be payments made with the aim of pushing employees' performance towards higher targets. And it could also be defined as compensation other than basic wages or salaries (Ugwu and Coker,2012).

Employees are to work smarter and harder with the hope of receiving financial compensation over and above their normal pay. Financial compensation has been proved to be effective in improving work quality and reducing project time and cost (Najimu, 2010).

Money, whether it is in the form of wages, piecework or any other compensation pay, bonuses, stock options, company-paid insurance, or any of the other things that may be given to people for good perception, is important. The way to ensure that money has meaning, as a reward for accomplishment and as a way of giving people pleasure from accomplishment, is to base compensation as much as possible on employees' perception (Pamela, 2015).

There are major components of a salary structure to use it as a motivating factor. These are the job rate, which relates to the importance the organization attaches to each job; payment, which encourages workers or groups by rewarding them according to their performance; personal or special allowances, associated with factors such as scarcity of particular skills or certain categories of information professionals or librarians, or with long service; and fringe benefits such as holidays with pay, pensions (Forson, 2012).

Payment by Result is historically the most widely used compensation scheme, it rewards employees according to the number of items or units they produce or the time they take to produce them. This scheme has been criticized due to its tendency to reward quantity of output rather than quality which can lead to reduced quality of the product or service. There is a great need to modify and evaluate the effectiveness of this scheme if it is to retain the impact of productivity. And skills-based pay is an input-based payment system in which employees receive pay for the skills or competencies which they acquire. This system gives the employees an opportunity to influence their pay by acquiring more skills that lead to pay increases. Skills-based pay encourages multitasking and flexibility, which in turn enables the organization to respond faster and more effectively to the needs of customers (Carolina, 2010).

There are compensations like commissions which are given based on a percentage of total sales. Used typically with sales people, commissions intended to act as an incentive and a means of recognizing achievement (Armstrong, Michael, Taylor and Stephen, 2014).

This scheme is claimed to increase employees' commitment to their company by linking pay to profit, and hence improve the level of mutual interest. Profit sharing also encourages the thought of everyone being on the same team; the employees have the same goals and are rewarded equivalently. From the employee's point of view profit sharing has disadvantage on the fact that pay levels may decline if the company do not meet its profit expectations (Carolina, 2010).

Gain-sharing on the other hand is the payment of cash sums to employees related to the financial gains made by the company because of its improved performance (Armstrong, Michael, Taylor and Stephen, 2014). There is a rapid and immediate impact on the individual's efforts that motivate the individual to increase production and improve performance. The individual gains several psychological and social benefits as a result of enhancing his purchasing power to satisfy his needs of goods and services. But financial incentives alone are not sufficient unless assisted by other types of incentives. Their effects are limited to satisfy the biological needs of individuals and have a little impact after it reaches the limit of needs. Therefore individuals are not seeking to increase production for additional financial gains, thus cannot be financially motivated to contribute in increasing production except for a certain amount based on their efforts (Marwan, 2012).

Wages and salaries: Wages and salaries are the remuneration paid or payable to employees for work performed on behalf of an employer or services provided.

Bonus: is an extra payment over and above salary and it acts as an incentive to perform better. It is linked to the profitability and productivity of the organization.

Tips: is a payment received for providing an excellent service

Promotion: Promotion is attached with increase in pay, and this motivates the employee to perform better. **Commission:** is a sum of money paid to an employee up on completion of a task or set performance

2.1.2.2. Indirect (Non-Financial) Compensation

Compensation of this type relies on increasing an employee's sense of satisfaction in his or her work. It is based on Management's recognition that an employee's work is valuable to the business as a whole, and providing employees with the feeling that the project undertaken is inherently meaningful (Najimu, 2010). Non-financial compensation schemes are aimed at moral motivation to serve in the interest of the community. Usually it attracts certain kind of people who readily

identifies the mission of the organization. It could be in the form of participate in decision-making, certificates of thanks and appreciation, training and parties for distinguished employees (Ugwu & Coker, 2012).

Non-financial incentives are those related to aspects of psychological needs, the increased attention to this aspect came after the emergence of human relations theories. Those incentives are based on respect of a human being who has feelings, hopes and aspirations. It could be in the form of participate in decision-making, training, certificates of thanks and appreciation (Marwan, 2012).

Recognition is the demonstration of appreciation for a level of performance it can be confidential or public, causal or formal. It is always in addition to pay. Recognition and appreciation of job effort to employee increase individual's satisfaction and loyalty to work, enhance more cooperation with colleague (Marwan, 2012).

According to (Carolina, 2010) there are different types of recognition:

Verbal and Written Recognition: - are for example expressions of admire or a personal gratitude note. This kind of recognition costs nothing and it makes people feel good.

Work-Related Recognition: - it could be educational and training opportunities, lateral or vertical career opportunities, a special project assignment, and work equipment.

Social Recognition: - This could be pizza parties, dinners and articles in newsletters.

Financial Recognition: - such as; cash, stock options and stock grants.

Symbolic Recognition: - It includes T-shirts, sculptures, coffee mugs and jackets. The importance does not lie on the monetary worth but on what the recognition symbolizes

Tangible Recognition: - consists of gift certificates, meal tickets, trips, merchandise and tickets to entertainment events. Recognition, whether it is cash or non-cash has an advantage over base pay and variable pay because it can be used at any time. Companies can immediately reward and acknowledge something of importance that was not necessarily planned, such as unexpected and outstanding achievements of individuals and teams. Non-cash recognition can be especially meaningful to the recipient since it can be customized or personalized. Non-cash recognition also gives the company a possibility to distinguish themselves from other employers due to the fact that this type of recognition cannot be imitated by other companies (Carolina, 2010).

Promotion is a movement of a position in which responsibilities and presumably prestige are enhanced. And empowerment is also the process which enables employees to set their own work goals and solves problems within their sphere of responsibility and authority can be considered as incentives (Khan & Gautam, 2014).

Some type of indirect composition offered by today organization (Byars & Rul 2008), this include social security, workers compensation, retirement plan, paid holiday and paid for vacation etc.

2.1.3. Compensation Strategy

A Compensation Strategy is a plan that dictates how employees are paid and rewarded for their work. These ideas are based on the current market for people with the same skills and the overall available funding a corporation is able to expend on payroll. Compensation strategy is also a means of motivation and incentive that increases the value of general payroll systems Compensation strategy is the method by which organizations attract and retain top talent. This system offers pay packages and annual rewards for ongoing loyalty to a business. It allows a firm to remain competitive with other organizations and helps companies set forth a strong impression of the goals they want to achieve. By generating a compensation strategy, organizations make a show of the skills they value and the type of personnel they want to attract. Creating a diverse pay range encourages employees to work hard and attain higher levels within the business to achieve more accolades and greater compensation (Shpetim, 2012).

2.1.3.1. Keys to an Effective Compensation Strategy

2.1.3.1.1. Budget Allocation

The strategy should include the organization's approach to allocating compensation dollars into salary and benefits. This strategy will determine how much of the total compensation budget will be spent on salary and what percentage will be spent on benefits and other incentives (Chappra, 2006).

2.1.3.1.2. Benefit Package

Many organizations use benefit packages, in addition to salary, to attract and retain employees. Their goal is to be competitive with health, retirement, tuition reimbursement and other benefits because they understand that it can be the determining factor for a job candidate who is deciding whether to accept a position with an organization, or an employee who is considering leaving (Chappra, 2006).

2.1.3.1.3. Performance Management System

It is important to have a structured performance management process to ensure employees are meeting corporate objectives and are assessed on a regular basis. This process should include development of annual goal annual performance appraisals and a structured process for coaching and mentoring employees. Compensation strategies can positively influence employee engagement and improve employee productivity (Chappra, 2006).

2.1.3.2. Compensation Strategy Alternatives

Compensation is an expense in the sense that it reflects the cost of labor (Dessler, 2011), often governed by compensation policies. As organization differ in size and purpose, so do in pay level.

Mathis et al. (2003) have identified three alternative strategies. These are:

2.1.3.2.1. The high-pay-level strategy

Under this strategy organizations choose to pay higher than the Average pay level that the market pays. The assumption is that a higher salary or wage will enable organizations attract and retain competent employees and this, in turn enhances Employee's productivity.

2.1.3.2.2. The low-pay-level strategy

In this alternative, the organization pays a minimum salary or wage to employees. This may be because a poor financial condition or the work doesn't require highly qualified personnel.

2.1.3.2.3. The comparable-pay-level strategy

This strategy requires organizations to follow “equal Pay for equal work”. In this strategy employees are paid based on comparable value of jobs they are performing within the company and/or the market.

2.1.4. Features of Compensation System

Compensation system refers to the sum total of monetary and non-monetary benefits offered to employees in return for their contribution to the organization. Every organization must have a compensation system that is understandable, workable and acceptable. According to Armstrong (2008), an organizational compensation system includes anything employees value and desire that an employer is able and willing to offer in exchange for employee's contribution.

According to Cole (2002), a compensation system can best be considered as a mechanism by which an organization plans how to attract, retain, reward and motivate its employees. It should provide a fair reward to those performing specified roles, and an incentive for employees in keeping pace with inflation.

Every organization is expected to build an effective compensation system in order to sustain in the competitive world. A fair and equitable compensation helps in maintaining good industrial relations by providing monetary and non-monetary benefits to all the employees. A fair compensation system always helps the organization in enhancing the satisfaction, productivity, performance, attendance and retention of employees (Ponduri & Aravind).

Well-designed compensation system enables organizations to attract qualified employees and retain and motivate the existing work force towards goal achievement. In designing compensation system, the amount to be paid and the organizations ability to pay must be considered. Some of the factors that influence compensation system design process are; employee participation, skilled based pay, pay secrecy, pay review, market rate, monetary versus non-monetary compensation (Decenzo & Robbins, 2001).

2.1.5. Employee Benefits

Bratton and Gold (2009) define employee benefits as that part of the total reward package provided to employees in addition to base or performance pay. Employee benefits focus on maintaining or improving the quality of life for employees and providing a level of protection and financial security for workers and for their family members.

Benefits are paid for being member of the organization. It provides protection against health and accident related problems and ensures income at the end of one's work life. For example, in United States legally required benefits includes social security, unemployment compensation, and workers compensation; private programs includes health care, life and disability insurance. Retirement income is provided through pension and saving plan (Randal, 1998).

Benefit programs also includes pay for time not worked for example, vacation, holydays seek leaves and absence pay, breaks and wash up and clean up time. According to Randal (1998), benefits provide firms the opportunity to attract and retain valued employees.

He identified several reasons why organizations pay much money into benefit programs. These include: attracting good employees, increase employee morale, reduce employee turnover, increase job satisfaction, motivate employees, enhancing the organizations image among employees and in the community and make better use of compensation Dollars.

Employee benefits include any benefits that employees receive in addition to direct compensation. They are indirect compensation because they are usually extended as a condition of employment and are not directly related to performance (John & Sons, 1982).

Benefits can act as noteworthy substitutes for wages. Employers may choose to offer fringe benefits since workers can have high tendencies for them. As a result, it can lead to decreasing the turnover rate as effectively as a similar valuable increase in wages (Dal, 2006). Woodbury also found that workers think of benefits as substitutes for wages. They are willing to exchange wages for more benefits. This can increase job satisfaction if the worker's income tax rate reduces by decreasing wages (Woodbury, 1983). Benefits are the additional non-cash items or service that have financial value and serve to make the employee's salary go further. Some benefits like sick pay and holiday pay are often legally mandated, whereas other benefits are discretionary (Crawshaw et al., 2014).

According to Pittsfield, benefits made available to employees are regarded as an addition to wages and salaries. Benefits may be direct benefit which includes profit sharing, sick pay, pension schemes, etc. and indirect benefits which include welfare amenities, social and recreational facilities, etc. Employee benefits should protect and promote wellbeing of employees. Some of the major benefits that organizations offer are; insurance (Life, Disability, Health), unemployment insurance, workers compensation, pension plans, payment for time not worked, severance pay, maternity leave, family and medical leave, annual vacation and others (Education grant, Tax exemptions, Loan scheme, Travel insurance, etc.)

Employee benefits have become an integral part of employee' s total income. The value of these benefits to both employers and employees however, depends on the employees' awareness of this costly part of employees' total compensations. Awareness refers to the employees' clear understandings about the fringe benefit packages in their work places (Danhower & Lust, 1996).

The major objective of benefit packages is to offer employees with benefits that are valuable enough to encourage them to stay longer with the company (Sinclair et al., 2005). Employee benefit program must; satisfy real needs, must meet individual employee needs, comply with legal requirements, have a wide range, be flexible to cope with changes in the environment. The benefit programs of an organization need to be communicated to employee through employee handbooks, brochures, employee calendars and employee meetings, so that they can have knowledge about the type and range of benefits being offered. (<http://www.busineaaknowhow.com>)

2.1.6. Compensation and Benefit Policy

Employee compensation and benefits policy refers to a set of beliefs and guiding principles which are consistent with the objectives of the organization. It guides the administration of monetary and non-monetary benefits (McGraw, 1993).

According to Gary (1994), compensation policies also include the amount of vacation and holiday pay, overtime pay policy, method of payment (i.e. weekly, biweekly, monthly) etc.

Compensation and benefits policy should (<http://www.study.com/academy/lesson>):

Provide employees with clearly defined and equitable strategies

Define company compensation and benefit opportunities; comply with legal requirements, and

Communicate the value of the benefits to current and future employees.

Schliemann (1987) in his article mentioned that organizations aim at maximizing their labor output by minimizing labor cost. Employee compensation and benefits package play a strategic role in raising organizational performance and profitability (Mangel & Useem, 2000).

Organizations need to communicate to employees about the compensation and benefits package being offered and must allow them to participate in the compensation and benefits decision making process. Employees are often unfamiliar with the value of their benefit packages. This is either in monetary terms or relative to the benefits received by others in the labor market. Research also shows that employees usually underestimate the value of their benefits (Wilson et al., 1985).

It is assumed that taking part in the process of choosing benefits will lead to a better understanding of the values of the benefits according to employees' opinion (Rosenbloom & Hallman, 1986). Benefits may also enhance benefit satisfaction by making employees more conscious and aware of the nature and worthiness of their benefits (Beam & McFadden, 1988). If employees can participate in the process of selection, they can have a better insight into what they get and a more positive perspective of the package.

2.1.7. Employees Perception towards Compensation and Benefits

According to Dulebohn and Werling (2007), the organizations ability to motivate workers and retain desired employees is largely influenced by compensation offered. Employee attitudes toward pay show decreases in favorable pay ratings among managers, exempt, and nonexempt employees. This is due to diminishing pay increases (due to lower inflation and lower merit increases); poor pay for performance relationships, and poor employee understanding of how pay is determined (Morgan & Schieman, 1986).

Organizations are struggling to offer benefit packages so as to meet employees' expectations and preferences. In this respect, the key to positively influencing employees is for the employers to offer benefits that employees view as important (Weathington & Tetrick, 2000).

Benefits offered by a company need to be positively perceived and valued by employees so that to have the intended influence on employee's behavior and attitudes (Iles et al., 1990). If the benefit is not positively valued by the employee, it falls within the employee's "zone of indifference" and the presence or absence of such benefit in the workplace have little effect to that employees (Kroeger, 1995). A benefit will be valued more highly if employees have accurate knowledge of the benefits offered to them (Tremblay et al., 1998).

Employees who have accurate view of their benefit coverage seem to have higher valuation of the benefits they receive and are satisfied with their benefit packages than employees who are less informed of their benefits (Dreher et al., 1988). Employee's attitude towards various benefits offered differs from employee to employee.

Compensation and benefits offered by the organization can have a dramatic effect on employees' attitudes to their job and the organization in which they work (Lincoln 1990). Thus, the rewards are used as a key tool to record behavior and activities in order to attract and retain the most competent employees and keep them satisfied and motivated (Wilcox et al. 1984, Bratton & Gold 2003, Rynes, Gerhart et al. 2004). Benefits are not linked with employee performance and for this reason some employees may perceive them as a part of the organizations social responsibility action. For employee benefits to be effective motivational tools, they must be properly administered. Adam (1999) argued that employee's perception of his pay in relation to other employees of similar status could affect the satisfaction, which he gets from the job. From his work, when there is a discrepancy between what he gets and his efforts in relation to what employees of similar status gets, the employee become dissatisfied with the job. Employee satisfaction is influenced by how much is received and how much the individual thinks should be received and also it is affected by comparisons with what happens to others. When an employee believes that someone else is making more money than that person really makes the potential for dissatisfaction increases.

2.1.7.1. Employee Pay Perception

Employees' pay perceptions are important in organization and it will impact the organization talent and business outcomes. But unfortunately, employees often have a negative view of their pay (Dunn & Martin, 2014). Employees usually do comparison regarding pay, and based on this comparison they made their perception. Employees feel unhappy or dissatisfied if they feel they are being paid less than their friends. Managers should effort so that employee believes their compensation is directly related with their performance and they had paid accordingly. Thus employee pay perception could be improved if they get right pay information at time from their supervisor or managers. Pay satisfaction is an important component of overall job satisfaction of employee. Employee job satisfaction highly influence by the compensation and its component. (Dunn & Martin, 2014).

Pay knowledge is the key of employee pay perception. If an employee's has limited pay knowledge, then they don't know how compensation system works, how they can earn more by giving better performance in organization (Diekmann, 2015). Employee pay perception depends on the pay information and communication, how clear or timely pay information organization provide to employee. When workers believe they receive pay communication on time, they create more positive perception towards organizational procedures, distributions, interpersonal treatment, and information (Day, 2011). If employees receive continuous pay information, their perception about pay system will be more positive. High pay knowledge leads to more pay satisfaction and perceived pay effectiveness at the organizational level (Sweins et al., 2009). Pay knowledge can be improve by shifting communications to focus on themes, helping employees to find information according to their preferences, and enabling managers to have actionable pay conversations, organizations can significantly improve the delivery of pay messages. These improvements also increase the impact of communication strategies on employees' pay perceptions. (Dunn & Martin, 2014).

Pay perception is also based on perceived fairness of compensation. Fairness is required in all organization decision, and the absence of fair policy lead to feelings of dissatisfaction and to perceptions of discrimination. Study found that pay satisfaction is depends on actual pay but it more depends on whether employee perceive pay policy as fair (Jawahar & Stone, 2011). Employee perceptions of unfairness are being related by many negative factors. These factors are generically called Counterproductive Work Behaviours (CWB) that is pay fairness as important pillar of pay

perception. If employee feel that benefit is distributed fairly they feel more motivated, but in lack of pay fairness employee feel less motivated and dissatisfied (Okpara, 2006).

However apart from pay fairness, Performance based pay was an important dimension affecting pay perception. It is an important factor influence the overall pay satisfaction of employee. Organization need to tightly link the pay and performance, because employee want pay equitable their performance level and should be improve with the performance improvement (Mone & Kim, 2008). Pay system have essential feature pay equity. Employee feel discrepancy if they found their pay is not equal to their contribution in the job. Pay perception is also differing on basis of sex, education and experience. Female has negative perception about pay and promotion policy of the organization as compare to male. Because male are more satisfied with organization pay and promotion (Okpara, 2006). Employee perceive pay policy ineffective if they found difference between individual objective and organization objective .Thus pay information, transparency in pay policy want pay to be linked with performance (Diekmann, 2015). To improve the pay perception of employee improvement is required in current compensation policy in form of better rewards system, performance bonds, introduction of employee stock option plan, other benefits based on performance.

2.1.8. Role of Company Incentive Schemes in Enhancing Employees Performance

Incentives force employees to behave in certain ways on any given day; they may choose to work as hard as possible at a job, to work just hard enough to avoid a warning and punishment. Organization use different and variety of incentives to reward employees in order to get work performance, but an organization need to consider using the best employee incentives to get the desired results (Falola et al., 2014).

Individual employee is motivated by different incentives or benefits and it is important to know how they are motivated and what can satisfy them in order to encourage them to have right attitudes to work which will invariably enhances employee performance and organizational productivity. Intrinsic motivators are critical in meeting a person's needs, because they describe a pattern of how an individual may behave (Marwan, 2012).

In competitive environment organizations are forced to consider strategies that will help them become more innovative, productive, and efficient in the industry by considering the need to remain competitive. By using innovative compensation strategies such as incentive programs which are

developed with an attempt to align individual motivation and goals with the objectives of the organization. Using Incentive programs with other innovative work practices including flexible job assignments and employment security has positive impact on performance (Reddy & Karim, 2013).

Compensation and benefit, in this research, represent monetary, such as basic pay- salary, incentive pay- bonus, and commission; and non-monetary such as medical insurance, life insurance, disability income, pension, social security, vacations, holiday, sick leave, low cost or free meals. However, benefits represent medical, retirement, housing, insurance coverage, life and disability insurance (Bhavani et al., 2016).

2.2. Empirical Literature Reviews

According to Beruk (2015) study on assessment on professional employee turnover causes at bank of Abyssinia. The study adopted a descriptive research design to identify the employee turnover causes. The research investigated the reasons why professional employees leave bank of Abyssinia and the reasons why they stay in the bank. Hence, the study revealed that the bank has not attractive salary and benefit package, the employee employer relationship was not good, there is job security problem, the employee reward program was not competitive, the work place were unfavorable, employees were handled unfairly and irrespectively. The study recommended that the bank need compensation policy, retention scheme policy, modify promotion policies to implement zero-discrimination, implement more aggressive reward and recognition program and create conducive working environment to retain its experienced and qualified employees.

Seifu, (2014), conducted a study on Compensation management practice in Ethio-Telecom. The study investigates compensation management practice in Ethio-telecom by analyzing the link between compensation package, job satisfaction, motivation and job performance. The study used multi stage sampling procedure to select 368 respondents. Data's are analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics such as correlation, mean score and standard deviations. The result indicated that employees are somehow satisfied with some of their compensation and benefit package and this could not be taken as the best compensation management practices of the organization. The researcher recommends that equitable and holistic compensation packages are more likely to attract, develop, motivate and retain qualified and competent personnel.

Tilahun, (2015) assess the study on the title: Assessment of compensation strategy in some selected private commercial banks in Ethiopia. The study was conducted in three private commercial banks, where 348 sample populations was selected from these banks, and questionnaire and interview was used to examine the attitude of employees towards the compensation strategy of their respective bank. The result of the study revealed that the effectiveness of compensation strategy of their respective bank has not been evaluated and the policy was not revised for long time. The researcher recommends that the compensation strategy of the bank and compensation policy should be periodically revised taking in to account the market conditions and the current performance of the employees.

Most people work for a living. It is rational that employees demand an appropriate level of compensation for their effort. Such compensation may be offered in monetary (direct) reward, such as salary and bonus, or bundled with other non- monetary (indirect) reward such as medical insurance (Mondy, 2010).

There are indications that employees are more likely to stay when there is a predictable work environment and vice versa (Zuber, 2001). In organizations where there was a high level of inefficiency, there was also a high level of staff turnover (Alexander et al., 1994). Therefore, in situations where organizations are not stable, employees tend to quit and look for stable organizations because with stable organizations, they would be able to predict their career advancement.

Griffeth et al. (2000) examined the relationship between pay, a person's performance and turnover. They concluded that when high performers are insufficiently rewarded, they quit. If jobs provide adequate financial incentives, the more likely employees remain with organization and vice versa.

Becker (1975) indicated that higher paid employees are less likely to resign than lower paid employees. Human capital theorists say that firms pay skilled employees more than their unskilled counterparts, because skilled employees have higher marginal productivity. There are tangible evidences to support negative relationship between salary level and turnover.

Harman et al., (1999) that negative job attitudes (e.g. low levels of job satisfaction) is one of the causes of leaving. In their seminal work, March and Simon (1958) proposed a psychological explanation of turnover that is based on individuals' utility functions: when outcomes (such as pay or promotion opportunities) are too low relative to the employees expectations, an employee becomes dissatisfied and motivated to leave.

Yohanes, (2014) also assesses the study on the title: factors affecting employee turnover and its impact on Ethiopian Evangelical church Mekaneyesus. The study has applied stratified random sampling techniques by choosing 75 existing employees and 11 employees and also used purposive sampling technique to choose 3 department heads. As per the findings of the study dissatisfaction with pay structure, mismanagement, unfair reward and promotion systems were some of the factors for employee turnover. The researcher has further concluded that lack of career advancement, job dissatisfaction, and leader's unwillingness to allow staff participation in decision making, and unfair training system were core factors for turnover.

Sajjad et al., (2013) conducted a study on the title: The impact of motivation on employee turnover in banking sector of Pakistan: the researcher used a total sample of 106 collected from branches of different banks, Descriptive statistics are used to describe the basic features of the data in a study. The result of the study shows motivation significantly affect employee turnover in banking sector which suggest that when motivation increase it would reduce the value of employee turnover in banking sector.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This chapter includes the research design, research approach, sample size, sampling procedures, data collection methods and data analysis method.

3.1. Research Design

A research design stands for advance planning of the methods to be adopted for collecting the relevant data and the techniques to be used in their analysis, keeping in view the objective of the research and the availability of staff, time and money (Kothari, 2004). The design constitutes the blue print for the collection, measurement and analysis of data. Designing a study helps the researcher to plan and implement the study in a way that will help the researcher to obtain intended results, thus increasing the chances of obtaining information that could be associated with the real situation (Burns & Grove, 2001).

So, descriptive research design was used because the researcher wants to describe the frequency, mean and standard deviations since it is preferable method to find existing facts, practices and phenomena as they are and finally interpret it to compare and contrast the difference based on means of independent sample T-test, which is an inferential statistical test that determines whether there is a statistically significant difference between the means in two unrelated groups. Moreover, cross sectional survey was used to collect all relevant data at a single point in time.

3.2. Research Approach

According to Dawson (2002) quantitative research approach allows for the collection of numerical data, the use of statistical procedures to analyze and develop inferences from that data, then measurement of variables, and the prediction. Therefore, in the study quantitative research approach will be used to develop inferences from the collected data because it helps to cover larger target groups in short period. So, quantitative data was gathered using objective items through questionnaires.

3.3. Population of the Study

According to Hair et al. (2010), target population is said to be a specified group of people or object for which questions can be asked or observation made to develop required data structures and information.

In assessing government and private banks, researcher confirmed that there were one government and eleven private Commercial Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia. From these, the researcher purposively selected only Commercial Bank of Ethiopia as the government Bank and also Nib International Bank as the private bank because these banks were the first banks that established in Gurage Zone (source from banks). Both banks had different branches in Gurage Zone woreda and city administration, in 12 woreda and 5 cities administration. The researcher also purposively selected Wolkite and Butajera cities and Cheha woreda administrations because these branches have existed much earlier or they were the first banks in Gurage Zone than other branches and they had large number of employees than the other branches that exists. Moreover, the researcher assumes that compensation and benefit policy of a bank in every branch is almost similar across its branches and the data collected from some selected respondents from a bank can be replicated and projected for the rest of the employees as well.

So, the target population of the study was employees or officers or clerks of two Banks (Commercial Bank of Ethiopia and Nib International Bank) Wolkite and Butajera cities administration branches; and Cheha woreda administration. According to the human resource department of wolkite, Butajera and Cheha branch of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia and Nib International Bank, the total clerks working at this time was 215 male and 94 female. Hence, the total population of the selected banks was 309 officers or clerks.

3.4. Sample Size

According to Alreck and Settle (2005) the choice of sample size is normally made after considering statistical precision, practical issues and availability of resources. On the other hand, Tabachnick and Fidell (2001) noted that samples are selected on a random basis and those samples are considered as representative of the population. A different sampling standard by Lowler (1984) noted that there is no a single precise way for the determinations of sample size hence there are a number of inadequacy for deciding on sample size. Malhotra and Peterson (2006) stated that, the larger the sampling size of research, the more accurate the data generated.

However, due to time and financial limitations and the nature of the population, to determine the sample size of the study, the researcher will use Yamane's (1967) formula. He provided a simplified formula to calculate the sample size.

This formula is based on a 95% desired confidence level and a 5% desired level of precision. $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$,

Where: **n**= Sample size required for the study;

N= total population size;

e = Level of precision

$n = 309 / (1 + (309 * 0.05^2))$, Where $N = 309$ and $e = \pm 0.05$

$n = 174$

As sample size, 174 (56.3%) participants were selected in this study from the total population.

3.5. Sampling Techniques

Sampling techniques can be divided into two types, probability or representative sampling and non-probability or judgmental sampling. Probability sampling is a selection of sampling techniques in which the chance or probability of each case being selected from the population is known. While, non probability sampling is a selection of sampling techniques in which the chance or probability of each case being selected is not known (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007).

Stratified sampling is where the population is divided into strata (or subgroups) and a random sample is taken from each subgroup. A subgroup is a natural set of items. Subgroups might be based on company size, gender or occupation. Stratified sampling is often used where there is a great deal of variation within a population. Its purpose is to ensure that every stratum is adequately represented (Ackoff, 1953).

The researcher used stratified sampling method of probability sampling techniques. The reason behind deciding to use stratified sampling method will be to ensure proportional representation of each types of strata and to give equal chance of being included in the sample. The basis for stratification in the study was geography, gender and branches of each bank.

Table 3.1. Stratified random sampling, regarding population size of employees of two Banks- Commercial Bank of Ethiopia and Nib International Bank (FEB., 2022)

Selected Banks		Branches of each banks	Number of officers or clerks or total population		Sample drawn (TP*0.563)			
			M	F	M	F	T	
CBE	CBEWB	Yejoka	15	6	8	3	11	
		Bekur	14	7	8	4	12	
		Wolkite	13	5	7	3	10	
		Buhari	7	4	4	3	7	
		Gubre	5	2	3	1	4	
	CBEBB	Iresha	17	6	10	3	13	
		butajira	16	5	9	3	12	
		erinzaf	18	6	10	3	13	
		fethi	15	5	8	3	11	
	CBECEB	Imdibir	11	4	6	3	9	
	TOTAL		131	50	73	29	102	
	NIB	NIBWB	Yejoka	12	7	7	4	11
			Halal	10	5	6	3	9
wolkite			13	4	7	2	9	
NIBBB		Iresha	11	6	6	3	9	
		zebidar	8	5	5	3	8	
		Zebidar halal	10	5	6	3	9	
		ker	11	6	6	3	9	
NIBCB		Imdibir	9	6	5	3	8	
TOTAL		84	44	48	24	72		
GRAND TOTAL		215	94	121		53		

3.6. Source of Data

According to William et al. (2010), there are two types of data, primary and secondary. The primary data are those which are gathered for the first time and a fresh and thus collected for the case at hand (Kothari, 2004). Secondary data is defined as data that has been previously collected for some purpose other than the one at hand.

In order to get relevant information for the study the researcher used primary sources of data. The primary data was gathered from employees in the selected organizations. The primary source of data was collected through questionnaires. Moreover, the researcher used secondary data through theoretical and empirical study comprised of different research studies, journals, articles, books and internet websites dissertations and reports with relevant literature.

3.7. Data Collection Method

According to Bhattacharjee (2012), survey research is research method involving the use of standardized questionnaires to gather data about people and their thoughts, behaviors and preferences in a systematic manner. So, in the study survey research method was used. The questionnaire was distributed to randomly selected sample of employees of the selected banks. Then, the questionnaire was collected physically from the potential respondents at their site by the researcher and the personnel that were assigned by the researcher for the purpose of data collection.

3.8. Data Collection Instrument

The researcher used questionnaire as data collection instrument. Close-ended questionnaire was developed from previous study with some modification. The questionnaire have three parts, the first part explains the purpose of the questionnaire; the second part is comprised of demographic profile of respondents while the third part is comprised of main research questions.

The questionnaire was prepared using 5 point Likert-scale approaches (Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree). Accordingly, respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement on 5 point Likert scale with the following ratings; Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), neutral (3), Agree (4) and Strongly Agree (5).

3.9. Reliability and Validity Tests

3.9.1. Reliability

According to Bhattacharjee (2012) reliability is the degree to which the measure of a construct is consistent or dependable. Reliability test is used to assess consistency in measurement items. If a research tool is consistent, stable, predictable and accurate, it is said to be reliable. The greater degree of consistency and stability of an instrument meant greater its reliability.

The researcher determined reliability of the questionnaire by calculating Cronbach's Alpha as reliability test. If a coefficient alpha is between 0.6 and 0.7 it indicates that there is fair reliability, higher Alpha coefficients indicate higher scale reliability (Joseph & rosemary, 2003).

3.9.2. Validity

Validity is defined as how much any measuring instrument measures what it is intended to measure. Bryman and Bell (2003) suggested that the important issue of measurement validity relates to whether measures of concepts really measure the concept. So, the questionnaire was adapted by reading different research thesis and literature review which is written by different scholars carefully and some adjustments were made. Moreover, the questionnaire was approved by the researcher's advisor before distributing to the respondents.

3.10. Data Analysis Method

The analysis starts by reporting information about the samples questionnaire that was distributed and returned. Then, the obtained data were summarized, organized, tabulated, coded, and analyzed using SPSS-20. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. Hence, in the study, data was recorded, described, interpreted, analyzed & compared.

To summarize demographic data descriptive statistics including frequency was analyzed using tables and percentages. Similarly, to summarize and compare the main research data, descriptive statistics mean, standard deviation, frequency distribution and percentage was used in the analysis step.

Two-sample independent t-test was used to investigate the research question. The two-sample mean, independent groups-government and privet banks employees, t-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference on employees' perceptions level towards compensation and benefit policy.

3.7. Ethical Considerations

The researcher can ensure that the entire process of the research was performed under ethical guidelines. To make sure all selected participants were well aware of the research objective, process and the outcome, they were provided with all research related information. This included the physical and emotional risks associated with the research. Participants were entitled to know about timeframe, scope, involved parties, implications as well as contributions of the research. Also participants were reasonable capacity, maturity and free to respond the questions without condition, hesitation, pressure or force. Participants were fully respected and there was no obligation to fulfill our research requirements and they were free to stop participating at any point. Thus, the researcher can ensure that the nature of the research was honest, open and friendly with no intention to harm participants, especially psychological and emotional harm. All information provided was kept confidential. The information collected from the survey was solely used for the research. The information obtained from the survey was analyzed based on the theoretical and practical approaches of the research.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1. Introduction

This chapter deals with presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered from employees using questionnaire. Data was collected and analyzed in order to compare employees’ perception towards compensation and benefit policy of Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia. As stated under the methodology part, to collect the data from employees, questionnaires were prepared and distributed to selected employees. In this study, 174 questionnaires were distributed, 102 to Government and 72 to private banks employees, and 170, which are 97.7% of total distributed questionnaire was collected, 99 from the Government and 71 from the private banks, and the rest was not returned because employees were very busy on work and they do not want to respond. From these only 168 respondents questionnaires were found to be valid, 98 from the Government and 70 from the private banks which is 96.6% of the total distributed questionnaires.

4.2. Reliability Test Results

Reliability is defined as means researchers evaluate their instruments if it give the same result at any time in the same condition or about its consistency (Adams,Khan, Raesaide and white,2007). Likewise, Sekaran and Bougie (2016) indicated that reliability scores less than 0.60 are poor, those scores in the range of 0.70 are acceptable, and those values greater than 0.80 are good.

Table 4.1 Variables Cronbach's Alpha values

Reliability Statistics

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Fairness of Compensation and Benefit	0.631	4
Effectiveness of Compensation and Benefit	0.621	8
Compensation and Benefit Decision and Administration	0.638	8
compensation and benefit policies	0.611	9

Source: Survey data result, 2022

As indicated in table 4.1, the Cronbach’s alpha coefficients for fairness of compensation and benefit, effectiveness of compensation and benefit, compensation and benefit decision and administration and overall compensation and benefit policies were between 0.60-0.70 which show acceptable level values.

4.3. Descriptive Statistics

4.3.1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The demographic profile of 168 employees, who were participants of the study, is summarized below in the form of frequencies and percentages.

Table 4.2: Frequency table of demographic profile of the respondents

Demographic variable	Category	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Sex	Male	116	69.1	69.1
	Female	52	30.9	100.0
	Total	168	100	
Age	18-30	79	47.1	47.1
	31-40	53	31.5	78.6
	41-50	22	13.1	91.7
	51-60	14	8.3	100.0
	Total	168	100.0	
Educational level	Certificate	18	10.7	10.7
	Diploma	35	20.8	31.5
	Degree	100	59.6	91.1
	Master	15	8.9	100.0
	Total	168	100.0	
Marital status	married	83	49.4	49.4
	unmarried	75	44.6	94.0
	divorce	8	4.8	98.8
	widow	2	1.2	100.0
	Total	168	100.0	
Work experience	1-5 year	64	38.1	38.1
	5-10 years	45	26.8	64.9
	10-15 years	31	18.5	83.4
	15-20 years	15	8.9	92.3
	more than 20 years	13	7.7	100.0
	Total	168	100.0	

Source: Survey data result, 2022

As far as gender characters' of respondents is concerned table 4.2., above shows that, 69.1% of the respondents were male while the rest of 30.9% were females. This implies that men and women involved in the study that the findings of the study did not suffer from gender bias.

In terms of age of respondents is concerned table 4.2., showed that, 47.1% of the respondents were within age group of 18-30 years, 31.5% of the respondents reported belong to 31 to 40 years of age group. The remaining 13.1.6% and 8.3% of the respondents were belonged to 41 to 50 years of age group and 51- 60 years of age groups, respectively. The age group result indicated that respondents were well distributed in terms of their age groups and more than half of staffs (78.6%) were young and have an age between 18 - 40 years. This implies that the respondents were comprised of heterogeneous groups; which in turn enabled the researcher to get varied responses across the sample units fairly distributed. Hence, this result indicates that the majority of the respondents were matured enough to provide reliable information with regard to the issue under study. Therefore, again the study did not suffer from age group bias.

In terms of marital status are concerned, table 4.2 showed that, 49.4% of employees were single; 44.6% were married; 4.8% were divorced and 1.2 % was widowed. This implies that almost half percent of respondents have experience of marriage.

As to qualification of the respondents (table 4.2), 10.7% of respondents hold certificate, 20.8% of respondents hold diploma, 59.6% of them were degree holders and 8.9% of respondents were master's holders. This shows that most of them (90%) hold adequate qualifications in relation to the jobs, which greater than diploma.

When organizational experience was examined, it can be seen from table 4.2, 38.1% of academic staffs worked for 1- 5 years; 26.8% of them had an experience between 5-10 years; 18.5% had tenure between 10-15 years, 8.9% of them had tenure between 15-20 years and only 7.7% of them worked more than 20 years in the organization. This information suggested that most of the employees 64.9% had less than 10 years services.

Finally combination of different age, education level and service of participants in the study area were found to be satisfactory to get reliable data for the study.

4.3.2.Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.3. Employees Perception Level towards Compensation and Benefit Components

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Fairness	168	2.3125	.91550
Effectiveness	168	2.2879	.67304
Decision and administration	168	2.3839	.71782
Policy	168	2.8869	.67989
Valid N (listwise)	168		

Source: Survey data result, 2022

Table 4.3 showed the employees perception level towards compensation and benefit results for descriptive statistics of fairness, effectiveness, decision and administration and Policy. Descriptive analysis revealed that fairness had a mean value of $M = 2.3125$ and standard deviation of $SD = .91550$; the effectiveness had a mean value of $M = 2.2879$ and $SD = .67304$; decision and administration had a mean value of $M = 2.3839$ and standard deviation of $SD = .71782$; and Policy had a mean value of $M = 2.8869$ and $SD = .67989$.

4.4. Inferential Statistics

Comparative analysis is the process of comparing items to one another and distinguishing their similarity and difference. When a business wants to analyze an idea, problem, theory or questions conducting a comparative analysis allows it to better understand the issue and form strategies in response.

4.4.1. Comparative analysis of Government and Private Banks based on Employees Perception Level of towards Fairness of Compensation and Benefit

The two-sample (independent groups) t-test is used to determine whether the unknown means of two populations are different from each other based on independent samples from each population. If the two-sample means are sufficiently different from each other, then the population means are declared to

be different. But prior to using the t- test, there is one major consideration that should be addressed. That is the population variance should be equal.

Accordingly, equality of variance must be checked by using F-test (Levene’s test) and to decide which t-test results to use, we must look at the significance level (Sig.) of Levene’s Test for equality of variances. If the significance level is greater than .05, then we can assume that group variances are equal and need to use the first row of t-test results. If the significance level is .05 or less, then we should assume that the group variances are not equal and need to use the second row of t-test results.

Moreover, to determine whether there is significant difference among the group, we need to look at the p-value for the equal variances and if $p > 0.05$, we assume that there is no significant differences between two groups and if $p < 0.05$, the difference between two group is assumed to be significant.

Table 4.4, Levene's test for Fairness of Compensation and Benefit based on Bank types

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means		
	F	Sig.	t	df	
Fairness	Equal variances assumed	1.285	.259	-2.093	166
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.071	142.815

Source: Survey data result, 2022

As shown in table above Levene's test of equality of variance are found to be acceptable and the researcher took the first row of the table value since Sig. values found to be greater than 0.05.

Table.4.5, A t-test showing Bank type difference in fairness of compensation and benefit

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P(.05)	
Fairness	Government Bank	98	2.1888	.88156	.038
	Privet Bank	70	2.4857	.94013	

Source: Survey data result, 2022

Accordingly, on average, Privet Bank employees had higher perception level of employees towards fairness of compensation and benefit within the bank ($M = 2.4857$, $SD = 0.94$) than Government bank ($M = 2.1888$, $SD = 0.88$). The difference between these two group was statistically significant with $t(166) = -2.093$, $p < .05$. Hence, the study result revealed significant difference between Government bank and Privet Bank on fairness of compensation and benefit.

4.4.2. Comparative analysis of Government and Private Banks based on Perception Level of Employees towards Effectiveness of Compensation and Benefit

The two-sample (independent groups) t-test is used to determine whether the unknown means of two populations are different from each other based on independent samples from each population. If the two-sample means are sufficiently different from each other, then the population means are declared to be different. But prior to using the t- test, there is one major consideration that should be addressed. That is the population variance should be equal.

Accordingly, equality of variance must be checked by using F-test (Levene's test) and to decide which t-test results to use, we must look at the significance level (Sig.) of Levene's Test for equality of variances. If the significance level is greater than .05, then we can assume that group variances are equal and need to use the first row of t-test results. If the significance level is .05 or less, then we should assume that the group variances are not equal and need to use the second row of t-test results.

Moreover, to determine whether there is significant difference among the group, we need to look at the p-value for the equal variances and if $p > 0.05$, we assume that there is no significant differences between two groups and if $p < 0.05$, the difference between two group is assumed to be significant.

Table 4.6, Levene's test for effectiveness of compensation and benefit for government and privet banks

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means	
		F	Sig.	t	df
Effectiveness	Equal variances assumed	1.215	.272	-2.137	166
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.175	157.411

Source: Survey data result, 2022

As shown in table above Levene's test of equality of variance are found to be acceptable and the researcher took the first row of the table value since Sig. value found to be greater than 0.05.

Table.4.7, A t-test showing difference in effectiveness of compensation and benefit for government and privet banks

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P(.05)
Effectiveness	Government Bank	98	2.1952	.69425	.034
	Privet Bank	70	2.4179	.62405	

Source: Survey data result, 2022

Accordingly, on average, Privet Bank employees had higher perception level of employees towards effectiveness of compensation and benefit within the bank (M =2.4179, SD = .62) than Government bank (M =2.1952, SD = .69).The difference between these two group was statistically significant with t (166) = -2.137, p<.05. Hence, the study result revealed significant difference between Government bank and Privet Bank on effectiveness of compensation and benefit.

4.4.3. Comparative analysis of Government and Private Banks based on perception level of employees towards compensation and benefit decision and administration

The two-sample (independent groups) t-test is used to determine whether the unknown means of two populations are different from each other based on independent samples from each population. If the two-sample means are sufficiently different from each other, then the population means are declared to be different. But prior to using the t- test, there is one major consideration that should be addressed. That is the population variance should be equal.

Accordingly, equality of variance must be checked by using F-test (Levene’s test) and to decide which t-test results to use, we must look at the significance level (Sig.) of Levene’s Test for equality of variances. If the significance level is greater than .05, then we can assume that group variances are equal and need to use the first row of t-test results. If the significance level is .05 or less, then we should assume that the group variances are not equal and need to use the second row of t-test results.

Moreover, to determine whether there is significant difference among the group, we need to look at the p-value for the equal variances and if $p > 0.05$, we assume that there is no significant differences between two groups and if $p < 0.05$, the difference between two group is assumed to be significant.

Table 4.8, Levene's test for compensation and benefit decision and administration based on Bank types

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means	
		F	Sig.	t	df
Decision and Administration	Equal variances assumed	1.423	.235	-2.606	166
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.582	143.655

Source: Survey data result, 2022

As shown in table above Levene's test of equality of variance are found to be acceptable and the researcher took the first row of the table value since Sig. values are found to be greater than 0.05.

Table.4.9, A t-test showing difference in compensation and benefit Decision and Administration of bank

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P(.05)
Decision and Administration	Government Bank	98	2.2640	.68908	.034
	Privet Bank	70	2.5518	.72840	

Source: Survey data result, 2022

Accordingly, on average, Privet Bank employees had higher perception level of employees towards compensation and benefit Decision and Administration within the bank (M =2.5518, SD = .73) than Government bank (M =2.2640, SD = .69).The difference between these two group was statistically significant with $t(166) = -2.606, p < .05$. Hence, the study result revealed significant difference between Government bank and Privet Bank on compensation and benefit decision and administration .

4.4.4. Comparative analysis of Government and Private Banks based on perception level of employees towards overall compensation and benefit policies

The two-sample (independent groups) t-test is used to determine whether the unknown means of two populations are different from each other based on independent samples from each population. If the two-sample means are sufficiently different from each other, then the population means are declared to be different. But prior to using the t- test, there is one major consideration that should be addressed. That is the population variance should be equal.

Accordingly, equality of variance must be checked by using F-test (Levene's test) and to decide which t-test results to use, we must look at the significance level (Sig.) of Levene's Test for equality of variances. If the significance level is greater than .05, then we can assume that group variances are equal and need to use the first row of t-test results. If the significance level is .05 or less, then we should assume that the group variances are not equal and need to use the second row of t-test results.

Moreover, to determine whether there is significant difference among the group, we need to look at the p-value for the equal variances and if $p > 0.05$, we assume that there is no significant differences between two groups and if $p < 0.05$, the difference between two group is assumed to be significant.

Table 4.10, Levene's test for overall compensation and benefit policies based on Bank types

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means		
	F	Sig.	t	df	
Policy	Equal variances assumed	.072	.789	-3.139	166
	Equal variances not assumed			-3.111	143.938

Source: Survey data result, 2022

As shown in table above Levene's test of equality of variance are found to be acceptable and the researcher took the first row of the table value since Sig. values are found to be greater than 0.05.

Table.4.11, A t-test showing difference in overall compensation and benefit policies of bank

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P(.05)
Decision and Administration	Government bank	98	2.7574	.65284	.034
	Privet Bank	70	3.0853	.68804	

Source: Survey data result, 2022

Accordingly, on average, Privet Bank employees had higher perception level of employees towards overall compensation and benefit policies within the bank (M =3.0853, SD = .68804) than Government bank (M =2.7574, SD = .65284).The difference between these two group was statistically significant with t (166) = -2.606, p<.05. Hence, the study result revealed significant difference between Government bank and Privet Bank on overall compensation and benefit policies.

4.5. Discussion of the Result

This section discusses the main findings of the research and makes comparisons with findings of previous researches.

The findings of the current study are totally consistent with works of:

In labor economics, labor market analysis is premised on the contention that there should be compensation parity for same nature of work in both the private and government organizations. Notwithstanding, the government policy trust of having comparable standards, much of the history of concern over government compensation and benefits have been that of low remuneration package. In spite of the rise of labor unions in the government sector in the USA, private organizations employees had better pay package than their government organizations counterparts (Bender & Heywood, 2010).

Smith (1987) in Bender & Heywood (2010) did a pioneering empirical research to examine the major methods of comparability between the government and the private organizations. The main trust of the study was to standardize for known earning components determining the pay package of a particular worker along the dimensions of education, training, experience, job location and other job-related attributes. Then, the average earning differentials between government and private organizations employees was compared to determine pay disparity between the two sectors.

Belman & Heywood (1995) conducted a population survey to establish pay comparability across (seven) 7 principal states in the USA. The highlight of the findings is that the pay differential was positive in 4 states and negative in 3 but when compared with Local Governments in the states studied, the differential was negative for the local government employees.

Borjas (2003) in Bender and Heywood (2010) studied public sector pay differentials using longitudinal studies from 1960s to 2000. The data indicated a fairly regular and consistent pattern over the study period for men employees but a relatively downward trend position for females in the public sector. By the end of his time, the remuneration differences were similar for both the gender translating to 9% lower in the local governments and 12% in the state governments.

Moreover, the study of Lee ((2004) is significant in comparability studies in public and private sectors. Using a longitudinal survey approach to study worker attributes, the results of the regression analysis indicates that female state government employees receive 3% lower than their private sector

counterparts while male employees at the local government earn basically the same with their private counterparts. Also, the study examines employee transition from one sector to the other which reveals some positive public sector differentials for women but largely no effect for men.

Furthermore, in a World Bank study, Glinskaya & Lokshin (2005) examine wage differentials between public and private sectors in India as well as the determining factors for employees' decision to join a particular sector. The major findings suggest that wages and remuneration disparity between the public and private sectors; the formal private and the informal sectors are positive and high. Comparing the research findings with global remuneration statistics, the study establishes that India has the highest pay differential between the public and the private sectors.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF RESULTS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter sketches brief summary of the study, conclusions of the study in accordance with the study results and forward recommendations based on the overall results of the study.

5.1. Summary of results

The researcher determined if there is significance difference between perception levels of employees towards compensation and benefit policy of government and private banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia. The study was conducted on Commercial Bank of Ethiopia as the government Bank and also Nib International Bank as the private bank. The following four research questions were raised: is there significance difference in perception level of employees towards effectiveness of compensation and benefit between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?, is there significance difference in perception level of employees towards fairness of compensation and benefit between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?, is there significance difference in perception level of employees towards compensation and benefit decision and administration between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia? And is there significance difference in perception level of employees towards overall compensation and benefit policy between Government and Private Banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia?

In order to meet the general objective, stratified random sampling followed by simple random sampling method was used. Based on the objective of the study and research questions questionnaire (survey instruments) for measuring the research variables were selected and organized. To collect the data from employees, questionnaires were prepared and distributed to selected employees. In this study, 174 questionnaires were distributed, 102 to Government and 72 to private banks employees, and 170, which are 97.7% of total distributed questionnaire was collected, 99 from the Government and 71 from the private banks, and the rest was not returned because employees were very busy on work and they do not want to respond. From these only 168 respondents questionnaires were found to be valid, 98 from the Government and 70 from the private banks which is 96.6% of the total distributed questionnaires.

Prior to applying regression analysis for testing research questions reliability test were carried out. With regard to reliability test the Cronbach's alpha coefficients for fairness of compensation and benefit, effectiveness of compensation and benefit, compensation and benefit decision and administration and overall compensation and benefit policies were between 0.60-0.70 which show acceptable level values.

The independent sample T-test result showed that respondents on average, Privet Bank employees perceived higher level of fairness in compensation and benefit (M=2.4857, SD=0.94) than Government bank (M =2.1888, SD = 0.88). Similarly, Privet Bank employees perceived higher level of effectiveness in compensation and benefit within the bank (M=2.4179, SD=.62) than Government bank (M=2.1952, SD=.69). Likewise, on average, Privet Bank employees perceived higher level compensation and benefit Decision and Administration within the bank (M =2.5518, SD = .73) than Government bank (M =2.2640, SD = .69). Moreover, on average, Privet Bank employees perceived higher level of overall compensation and benefit policies within the bank (M =3.0853, SD=.68804) than Government bank (M =2.7574, SD=.65284).

5.2. Conclusion

The aim of this study was to determine if there is significance difference between perception levels of employees towards compensation and benefit policy of government and private banks in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia. Two-sample independent t-test was used to investigate the research question. The two-sample mean, independent groups-government and privet banks employees, t-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference on employees' perceptions level towards compensation and benefit policy.

The study result revealed significant difference between Government bank and Privet Bank on fairness of compensation and benefit, effectiveness of compensation and benefit, compensation and benefit decision and administration and overall compensation and benefit policies.

5.3. Recommendations and Suggestions for Future Study

The researcher forwards the following recommendations to the banks and suggestions to other researchers.

5.3.1. Recommendations

- The management of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia develops compensation and benefit policy at the bank that focus on the real need of employee needs; and made compensation and benefit increment within logical time period.
- The management of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia develops compensation and benefit policy at the bank that focuses on adequacy, equitability, incentives for better performance, and secure employees from being exposed to unemployment and attract and retain competent employees.
- The management of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia develops compensation and benefit policy at the bank that focus on periodically updated and communicated, participation of employees in decision process, periodic evaluation of effectiveness and link organizations strategic plan.
- The management of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia develops compensation and benefit policy at the bank that focus on payments based on performance, appropriate payments for experience and qualification, support and facilitate achievement of organizational goals and allows employees to take up higher responsibilities
- The management of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia should seek for various ways of improving employees' performance in their company by finding out the effect, causes or problems associated the compensation and benefit scheme which will help them to identify those things that motivate their staff and apply them properly.
- Management of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia should purposefully need to work on employee retention mechanisms.

5.3.2. Suggestion for further Research

- Very few studies are found which shows compare employees' perception towards compensation and benefit policy that need greater concern. So, further research should be done on these aspects.
- Unfortunately, circumstances limited the present study to cross-sectional research design. Future research should be done on longitudinal research designs to investigate the effects more.
- Moreover, the study variables were fairness, effectiveness, decision and administration and compensation and benefit policies. Thus, there is a need for future examination of variables including other variables to compare government and private banks.

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YENEWUB WUDU (2017): DETERMINANTS OF EMPLOYEES JOB SATISFACTION (THE
CASE OF COMMERCIAL BANK OF ETHIOPIA, NORTH ADDIS DISTRICT
GRADE TWO CITY BRANCHES: ST.MARY'S UNIVERSITY

Appendix Questionnaire

Section 1 – Demographic Information

Please complete the following biographical information by circling your correct choice.

1. Gender 1.Male 2. Female
2. Age group 1.18-30 2.31-40 3. 41-50 4.51-60
3. Marital status 1. Single 2. Married 3. Divorced 4. Widowed
4. Educational level: 1.Diploma 2. Degree3.Master and above
5. Work experience in the College 1.1 to 5 years 2.6 to 10 years 3.11 to 15 years 4.16 to 20 years 5.above 20 years

Section 2- Employees Perception towards Compensation and Benefit Policy.

The following employees’ perception towards compensation and benefit policy questionnaires has three subparts: employees’ perception towards compensation and benefit policy fairness effectiveness and decision and administration questions. Please respond to the following questions on your perception towards compensation and benefit policy in your organization by putting a thick mark (√) in your option. Please choose from the following rating: Strongly disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, and strongly agree.

2.1. Fairness of compensation and benefit

No.	Items	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 strongly agree
1.	The compensation and benefit policy at the bank are focus on the real need of employee					
2.	The amount of salary and benefit I					

	received is fair relative to other banks					
3.	Compensation and Benefit adjustment /increment is made within a reasonable or logical time period					
4.	In your organization the type of compensation its provide based on employee option					

2.2. Effectiveness of Compensation and Benefit

No.	Items	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 strongly agree
1.	Compensation and benefits adequacy					
2.	Compensation equitability					
3.	Compliance-Government regulations					
4.	Incentives for better performance					
5.	Attract and retain competent employees					
6.	Balance between organization cost and employees contribution					
7.	Secure employees from being exposed to unemployment					
8.	Provide opportunity to attain self-interest					

2.3. Compensation and Benefit Decision and Administration

No.	Items	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 strongly agree
1.	Periodically updated and communicated					
2.	Employees participation in compensation decision process					
3.	The organization has written compensation and benefit policy					

4.	Periodic evaluation of effectiveness					
5.	Link to organizations strategic plan					
6.	Knowledge of where to go for information related to benefits					
7.	Understanding of how retirement benefits calculated					
8.	Provision of flexible benefit options					

2.4. Employees' perception towards overall compensation and benefit policies

No.	Items	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 strongly agree
1.	Payments based on performance					
2.	Appropriate payments for experience and qualification					
3.	Adequate payments for responsibility discharged					
4.	Payments have positive effect on employees productivity					
5.	The benefits are as good as other sector					
6.	Support and facilitate achievement of organizational goals					
7.	Comparable to what employees think should be					
8.	Current compensation system fulfills the psychological and self-actualization needs of employees.					
9.	Current compensation management system allows employees to take up higher responsibilities.					

